

PROTOTYPE SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLED DECONSTRUCTION PROCESS

Deliverable D5.2

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SHORT ABSTRACT	This deliverable will deliver a robotic deconstruction system that can adaptively plan and execute the deconstruction task by incorporating the XR technology as an interface
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CONTRIBUTOR(S)	Carsten Kamp, Chu Han Wu, Marit Zöcklein

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Executive Summary

While 5G has become a familiar term when speaking of private and public networks for communication, the use of 5G technologies in manufacturing, energy, construction or automotive is only at the beginning. This is the starting point for the TARGET-X project to take off. In a joint approach, research partners from these industries explore new use cases and applications. In the construction vertical, we will explore the potentials of 5G as a communication standard for construction machines to perform selected deconstruction activities and transition towards a more circular economy.

This deliverable complements the video for the demonstration of a prototypical deconstruction system, by incorporating XR technology for adaptive planning and execution of the tasks. The report includes the description of the setup and current status of the implementation.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIM - Building Information Modelling

LoD - Level of Detail

SDGs - United Nations Sustainable Developments Goals

CDW - Construction and Demolition Waste

FSTP - Financial Support to Third Parties

URLLC - Ultra-reliable low-latency communication

EMBB - Enhanced mobile broadband

ROS - Robot Operating System

MQTT - Message Queuing Telemetry Transport

SPARQL - Protocol And RDF Query Language

LiDAR - Light Detection And Ranging

YOLO - You Only Look Once (computer vision model that is used for object detection)

RGBD - Red Green Blue – Depth

XR - Extended Reality

AR – Augmented Reality

IoT – Internet of Things

CUDA – Compute Unified Device Architecture

GPU – Graphics Processing Unit

LBD – Linked Building Data

LOIN - Level Of Information Needed

1 Introduction

With the announcement of the "2030 climate action plan", the European Commission has expressed its intention to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 [1]. By accounting for 37% of all energy and process-related CO₂ emissions the construction sector is one of the largest emitters of greenhouse gases according to the 2022 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction [2]. At the same time, Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) caused by the construction industry is one of the major waste streams in the EU [3]. To meet these two challenges, development must necessarily abandon linear value chains and move towards closed-loop value chains in the sense of the circular economy [4]. In the context of a circular economy in construction, a linear chain follows a traditional "take-make-dispose" approach, moving resources through extraction, use and disposal, while a circular chain focuses on designing processes where materials and components are reused, recycled or repurposed, forming a closed-loop system that minimizes waste and maximize resource efficiency. However, this requires rethinking and reengineering traditional construction processes [5, 6].

The primary objective is to automatize construction processes utilizing 5G technology, which is already a well-established communication medium, to develop a prototype system for robotic deconstruction. This deliverable serves as a first approach, contributing to the reuse of building materials. In order to enable information visualization and machine control in real time on the construction site, Extended Reality (XR) technology will be incorporated into the workflow for the adaptive planning and execution of tasks.

1.1 Relations to other activities

The activities in work package 5 "construction" overlap with work package 3 "energy" and work package 1 "methodological assessment framework".

The collaboration with work package 3 is demonstrated with the Meter-X device. It is an energy measurement device, which was developed at the RWTH ACS department and integrated on the construction testbed. It is used to measure and understand energy consumption of different construction machinery. Details about the development and application of the test are explained in deliverable D3.4. Apart from that, there is overlap with the activities in work package 1 "Methodological assessment framework". Data obtained in work package 5 activities will also be used as input for the methodological assessment framework that will be built in work package 1 of TARGET-X.

1.2 Document overview

This document offers a comprehensive account of the TARGET-X project's progress, delineating each stage of its development and implementation. Section 2 introduces the Construction Testbed, which comprises a designated structure earmarked for deconstruction and serves as a basis for the deconstruction process. Furthermore, this section delineates the establishment of the 5G network at the Reference Construction Site, which serves to facilitate seamless communication between all components involved in the deconstruction process. Subsequently, chapter 3 provides a detailed account of the machinery employed in the project, with particular emphasis on both the principal deconstruction machinery and the supporting machinery. This chapter provides a detailed technical description of the configuration, functionality, and integration of the equipment within the overall setup.

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Chapter 4 explains of the core methodologies employed, with a particular focus on the utilization of XR (extended reality) applications in the planning and control of deconstruction tasks. The XR application for deconstruction planning facilitates the visualization and organization of tasks, whereas the XR application for machinery control enables the precise management of deconstruction machinery. Furthermore, this section addresses the safety assistant system, which was developed to ensure the security of human operators and robotic deconstruction systems.

The subsequent chapter 5 reflects on the outcomes of the prototype system for controlled deconstruction process, evaluating the achievements and challenges of the development. Finally, chapter 6 presents a forward-looking perspective on forthcoming work.

2 Prototype setup for robotic deconstruction

2.1 Construction test bed Reference Construction Site in Aachen

The Reference Construction Site of the RWTH Aachen University, operated by the Center Construction Robotics at Campus Melaten, is the designated large scale test bed of the construction vertical of the TARGET-X project. Figure 2.1 shows the view of the Reference Construction Site with the ReStage Structure in the middle. The ReStage Structure is a multi-material demonstrator, which was constructed by the partners who participated in the First Open Call as part of the Financial Support of Third Parties (FSTP) program. Timber, concrete, and steel elements were assembled into the structure at the Reference Construction Site in the summer of 2024, where the processes and partners tested 5G for a number of their processes. The structure will be utilized to demonstrate the deconstruction of a building element.

Figure 2.1 View of the Reference Construction Site with TARGET-X ReStage Structure

During the design of the structure, disassembly was defined as a functional requirement for each of the materials and especially for the connections of the different elements (see Figure 2.2).

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Figure 2.2 Explosion view of steel elements to show deconstructable connections of elements

Using BIM (Building Information Modelling) as a collaborative tool, it is possible to model different Levels of Detail (LoD) for the construction project, according to the needs of each phase (see Figure 2.3). LoD describes the necessary semantic and geometric information with a set of five different levels (LoD 1 - LoD 6) [5]. It can be applied to the deconstruction phase to model the level of detail required to execute the process.

Figure 2.3 Stages of a buildings' life cycle according to EN 15804 [6].

Table 1 Levels of detail equivalent to level of information need (LOIN) for a BIM model as defined by DIN EN ISO 19650 [7]

LOD	DEFINITION
LOD1 - SYMBOLIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Symbolic placeholder representing an object which may not be to scale or have any dimensional values. – This is particularly relevant to electrical symbols which may never exist as a 3D object.
LOD2 – CONCEPTUAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Simple placeholder with absolute minimum level detail to be identifiable, e.g. as any type of chair. – Superficial dimensional representation. – Created from consistent material: either ‘Concept-White’ or ‘Concept-Glazing’.
LOD3 – GENERIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – A generic model sufficiently modeled to identify type and component materials. – Typically contains a level of 2D detail suitable for the “preferred” scale – Dimensions may be approximate.
LOD4 – SPECIFIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – A specific object, sufficiently modeled to identify type and component materials. – Accurate dimensions. – A production, or pre-construction, “design intent” object representing the end of the design stages. – Suitable for procurement and cost analysis.
LOD5 – FOR CONSTRUCTION/ RENDERING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – A detailed, accurate, and specific object of the construction requirements and building components, including specialist sub-contract geometry and data. – Should include all necessary sub-components adequately represented to enable construction. – Used only when a 3D view at a sufficient scale deems the detail necessary due to the object’s proximity to the camera.
LOD6 – AS-BUILT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – As-Built a precisely modeled representation of the constructed object. – Any construction irregularities or eccentricities should be modeled.

Figure 2.4 shows the 3D model of the ReStage structure and the steel elements highlighted. Steel elements were selected for deconstruction in this project due to their distinctive advantages in terms of reusability, efficiency, and environmental impact [8]. Given the existing experience in concrete deconstruction, a shift in focus to steel allows for a contrasting perspective on sustainable deconstruction practices and a broader assessment of material reuse strategies [9].

Figure 2.4 3D Model of the ReStage Structure with highlighted steel elements

Within the ReStage demonstrator structure, one beam was selected for deconstruction. The beam is an HEB120 with a weight of approximately 50 kilograms, which is consistent with the deconstruction machine's ability to carry it [9]. At this stage of prototyping the use cases, the structural interdependencies of the selected steel beam have not yet been considered.

2.2 Communication Set up on Construction Site

The 5G cell covering the Reference Construction Site is part of the 5G Industry Campus Europe infrastructure [10]. It is a 5G non-standalone outdoor network running at 3.7-3.8G Hz. The emitting antennas are omni-directional. They are mounted on the mast of a tower crane for an elevated position overlooking the construction site. For compatibility with other commercial outdoor 5G networks a TDD2 pattern is used which translates into a Uplink/Downlink configuration of 10:2:2. The total uplink capacity is limited to approximately 80 Mbit/s. Furthermore, placed in one of the construction containers there is an edge server that serves as computing backbone for most use cases on the testbed.

Figure 2.5 Drone shot with visualization of the 5G network components of the Reference Construction Site.

3 Description of the prototype setup and use case components

3.1 Choice of deconstruction machinery

In the previous deliverable 5.1 [11], which described the development plan for the partially automated deconstruction process the BROKK 170 machine was selected as the machine to operate the deconstruction process. During the first phase (*Roadmap for the 5G/6G empowered deconstruction robotic platform*) of the project and the definition of the process requirements the, following arguments led to the change of the robot from the BROKK 170 to the KUKA KMR Iontec (see Figure 3.1, [9]):

1. Precision and Control

The mobile industrial robot offers a higher degree of precision compared to traditional hydraulic machines. In a partial deconstruction process, where specific elements need to be carefully removed without damaging surrounding structures, this precision is crucial. The robot's advanced control systems allow for fine-tuned movements and operations.

2. Flexibility and Adaptability

Conventional demolition machines like the BROKK 170 are designed primarily for heavy-duty tasks and full-scale demolition, which limits their flexibility in more delicate operations. The mobile industrial robot, on the other hand, is highly adaptable to a range of tasks. It can be reprogrammed or adjusted to handle various deconstruction techniques, making it suitable for the nuanced and complex requirements of partial deconstruction. This adaptability makes the robot a better fit for tasks that require both strength and finesse.

3. Flexibility on site

The Brokk 170 is a cable-bound construction machine. This limits the machine's mobility and adaptability on complex sites. The electric industrial robot, however, operates on a battery, offering enhanced mobility and flexibility. This cable-free design allows it to navigate easily across the site.

Figure 3.1 KUKA KMR Iontec on the Reference Construction Site

3.1.1 Hardware Specifications of the deconstruction robot

As seen in Figure 3.2 the KUKA KMR Iontec consists of various hardware specifications. The deconstruction robot has been designed with a mobile platform so that it can easily navigate the variable terrain commonly encountered on these sites. To ensure safe operation, the robot is equipped with a safety laser scanner, which monitors the surrounding environment to detect potential hazards. Stability is further enhanced by its extendable outriggers, which provide additional support during deconstruction tasks. The robot's adaptive base is designed to allow attachment of various end-effectors, offering flexibility for different deconstruction needs. For this project's use case, a magnetic gripper will be attached to handle steel beams effectively, aligning with the focus on steel as the chosen material for deconstruction. The manipulator on this robot also has a 70 kg payload capacity, ensuring it can manage the weight of steel elements efficiently during the deconstruction process.

Figure 3.2 Hardware Specifications of KUKA KMR Iontec

The dimensions of the safety zone around the deconstruction robot originate from its workspace as defined in the product data sheet provided by the manufacturer. The shape of the workspace is simplified to a cylinder and extended by 1m in each direction. The resulting, rotationally symmetric safety zone has the dimensions $r_{safety, KALI} = 3101mm$ and $h_{safety, KALI} = 4094mm$. This simplified definition is used further in the prototype for the safety assistant use case.

Figure 3.3 Technical drawings showing the dimensions of the Kuka KMR Iontec robot from which the size of the safety zone is derived [9].

3.2 Supporting machinery for deconstruction process

In the context of work package 5 of the TARGET-X project, the development of a Safety system for (de-)construction robots was defined as a task. For this project a mobile robot based on a commercially available platform by *Innok Robotics* [12] is used to support the deconstruction process. The platform possesses proprioceptive sensors for tracking of system states by design and has been updated with exterior sensors for observation of the environment. In contrast to the four-wheeled mobile robot described in deliverable D.5.1 [11], an existing three-wheeled mobile robot platform is used for reasons of availability. As the robots are from the same manufacturer and only have different wheel configurations, the change has no impact on the concept implementation. In addition, the three-wheeled robot has a trailer that can be used to transport objects e.g., disassembled components around the site.

The robot platform has dimensions 920 x 720 x 440 mm. The electric motor allows maximum speeds of 0,9 m/s with a battery life of up to 6 hours. The platform has a maximal loading capacity of 400 kg [12]. By design, the *Innok Heros* is equipped with the inertial measurement unit (IMU) *Xsens Mti-30* as well as wheel encoders for the purpose of odometry. Additionally, a 2D *SICK Laserscanner outdoorScan3 Core I/O* and a 3D Lidar scanner *Hisense XT16* for point cloud capturing are equipped for navigation. To enable communication with other PCs the 5G-capable router *UR75* from *Milesight* has been added. In addition, the equipment specified in section 4.3 for the implementation of the safety use case and for 5G communication is attached to the robot. The additional equipment is powered by a portable power station *Ecoflow Delta Max* also deployed to the mobile robot that is stored on trailer of the mobile robot platform.

Figure 3.4 Mobile robot platform Innok Heros 223 equipped with a 1) 3D LiDAR-scanner Ouster OS1 and a 2) 5G router Milesight UR75.

3.3 Communication via 5G

The deconstruction process, which was described in chapter 3 comprises of different hardware components, each communicating with the edge server via 5G. The 5G network ensures that all components are able to communicate efficiently and in real-time, which is critical for the coordination and control of operations. The following section explains the communication of each component:

3.3.1 Tablet/Operator to construction testbed edge server

The tablet serves as an interface for the operators, allowing them to interact with the system. Through the 5G connection, the tablet communicates with the edge server on the testbed to receive live data and visualizations of the ongoing process and the deconstruction structure. The operator can use the tablet to select tasks, make adjustments, or issue commands. These inputs are sent instantly to the server, which in turn relays them to the appropriate machines. To increase the level of control the operator has over the process, live feedback data from the camera mounted on the machine whilst the process is running, is sent to the tablet for further supervision. This two-way communication ensures that the operator has full control and access to up-to-date information at all times.

3.3.2 Mobile robot platform to construction testbed edge server

The mobile robot platform connects to the 5G network on the testbed through the attached router that holds a simcard registered to the network cell onsite. It receives path and target coordinates for

navigation from the edge server while it sends the observation logs from the human detection algorithm to the edge server as shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5 Schematic diagram of the communication setup. Solid lines represent wired connections with ethernet cables, dashed lines represent wireless connections via 5G.

4 Description of deconstruction process and test scenario

The implementation of a circular economy in the construction industry necessitates the development of novel approaches to the utilization of resources in a more efficient and waste-minimizing manner. A pivotal stage in this process is the non-destructive removal of components from existing structures to facilitate their reuse. Concurrently, deconstruction is frequently associated with elevated risks for personnel, which underscores the importance of automation through the utilization of robots. Robot-based deconstruction solutions can not only enhance safety by keeping individuals out of hazardous zones, but also markedly augment efficiency and precision during selective deconstruction.

Within the developed prototype system the deconstruction process begins by maneuvering the deconstruction robot to its designated location from where it will operate. The location is chosen such that the robot can reach and safely grab each element that is to be deconstructed during the process. Therefore, KUKA KMR Iontec is driven manually to the pre-planned spot for deconstruction. In the following the deconstruction robot is considered stationary as only the arm will move during the deconstruction process while the robots' base remains static. The positioning of the robot does not have to be precise as long as the building elements are within the reach of the robotic arms.

4.1 XR Application for deconstruction planning

The deconstruction process starts by scanning the identifier or marker on the structure using an XR (Extended Reality) device. With the support of the XR application, the operator can visualize the elements and joints of the structure, which can help in planning the deconstruction process. A SPARQL query [13] is created and transmitted to the edge server via 5G, requesting geometry data and deconstruction information. The server responds with a result, which is then retrieved and used to generate real-time meshes of different building elements. The generated model meshes are anchored onto the marker.

Figure 4.1 System architecture of the framework for the AR application with the edge server.

The information retrieved from the edge server is Linked Building Data (LBD) in the form of triples converted from Building Information Models (BIM) that were drafted by the different beneficiaries of the FSTPs for the materials timber, steel and concrete. The information includes the building elements for each connection within each assembly group and the assembly order for certain building assembly group. The system architecture of the framework is displayed in *Figure 4.1*. The queried information shows the users where the fasteners are in 3D space. These 3D models are

interactive, that SPARQL queries are being generated dynamically, of which information of the joints and fasteners are displayed and relayed to the operator.

Figure 4.2 Anchored model onto the steel structure. Highlighted in light red are all connections of the steel beams with plates to its neighboring elements for deconstruction planning

Figure 4.3 Interaction with elements generates dynamic SPARQL queries. On the top left shows the results of the query from for the respective element.

Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3 show a screen capture of the XR application being used in the context of steel structures while Figure 4.4 shows the application in the context of concrete. In both cases, information about the joints between neighboring elements can be queried from the triple store. Furthermore, in the case of concrete any internal elements like piping or wirings can be displayed. The assistance provided by the application allows the user to have better planning and take more informed actions when deconstructing any structure.

Figure 4.4 Connectors between elements and wiring components hidden within concrete are rendered and IFC information is relayed to the user.

4.2 XR Application for deconstruction machinery control

When the deconstruction robot has arrived at the pre-planned spot the deconstruction process is initiated. It consists of six steps:

1. Rough positioning
2. Precise positioning
3. Gripping
4. Unfastening
5. Lifting
6. Releasing.

For rough positioning, an AR application is deployed and is initiated using an Aruco marker that is attached to the KUKA KMR Iontec. Following that, the XR application is used to simulate and visualize the rough positioning path and way points. The confirmed result is then communicated to KUKA KMR Iontec and the process of deconstruction is carried out.

Figure 4.5 Aruco marker on KUKA KMR Iontec

The hologram of the KUKA KMR Iontec is instantiated in the application with reference to the Aruco marker. The operator can visualize an overlay of the articulated robot in the physical world as shown in Figure 4.6. The operator decides the target position of the end effector and manipulates the path of which it should take. The path is simulated and visualized in the AR application. The operator visualizes the positions of the path the robot takes and confirms if no collision is seen. The AR application then sends the simulated joint rotations to the on-board controller on the KUKA KMR Iontec and moves the arms. During this process, there is a camera mounted on deconstruction machine for the operator to further supervise the operating machine by having the data streamed to the application.

Figure 4.6 KUKA KMR Iontec with instantiated hologram anchored using the Aruco Marker

Figure 4.7 Simulation visualization of the path motion for each joint.

Figure 4.8 Motion is triggered, and the articulated arms move to the desired position.

Using framework as described by Wu et al in [14], the paths can be manipulated using different pathways to offer a more robust planning in a dynamic construction site environment. The AR application is designed to be robust and to be able to work with Internet of Things (IoT) enabled machines, which are mainly running on MQTT and ROS. The messages are written in a manner which is readable for both the frameworks and communication protocols using a MQTT2ROS bridge. The result shows that while it is able to move to the position according to the path, the precision of the positioning is however insufficient. Which leads to the second part of the motion, which is precise

positioning, which is to be developed. For the precise positioning, it is planned that the precise positioning takes over when another marker on the building element is within the range of the camera mounted on the end effector.

4.3 Safety assistant system for (de-)construction robots

As soon as the deconstruction robot is in place and the operator finishes the path planning for the deconstruction task, the operator leaves the deconstruction zone. Thus, he/she loses the immediate awareness of the scene. Additionally, the deconstruction robot itself might not be able to perceive “its complete workspace due to occlusion by the built structures. This can lead to dangerous situations, if a human worker or another machine approaches the active workspace around the deconstruction robot during deconstruction unnoticed by the remote operator.

Therefore, the operator sends the mobile robot platform Innok Heros 223 [12] to observe the workspace around the deconstruction robot. The robot receives task and position data from the operator and then navigates autonomously to the observation zone. To navigate autonomously, the mobile robot scans its environment and references itself to its surroundings by comparing the scanned points and edges with those in the BIM model of the site and the current construction progress via the 5G network. The successful self-referencing as shown in Figure 4.9, where scanned points are aligned with the edges of objects in the BIM model, is used as basis for navigation.

Figure 4.9: Screenshot from the AI web interface where the mobile robot uses a BIM Model as a navigation base. The red points (point cloud from the robot) are used to reference the robot to the digital model.

From the defined observation position the mobile robot platform scans the workspace of the deconstruction robot and checks for the presence of humans (see Figure 4.10). This is done by analyzing the point cloud recorded by the mounted 3D LiDAR-scanner Ouster OS1-128 with a modified YOLOv5-algorithm that was refined with a dataset of 800 labelled images generated from the reflectivity map of the LiDAR scanner as described by Kirner et al in [15]. The Ouster OS1 -128 is

a mid-range high resolution imaging LiDAR scanner that records a 360° point cloud with a horizontal resolution of 1024 points on a vertical resolution of 128 channels. Recording with a frequency of 10Hz the output data rate of UDP packets from the LiDAR to the connected router is up to 255Mbps. As mentioned in section 2.2 the uplink on the testbed is limited. Hence, the recorded point cloud is processed on board the mobile robot platform and only the result of the human detection algorithm is sent to the edge server via 5G.

Figure 4.10: Mobile robot observing the safety zone of the deconstruction robot as a schematic representation in the 3D model (left) and as point cloud recorded view the Ouster OS1-128 LiDAR scanner (right).

Since the YOLOv5-algorithm for human detection requires a CUDA-capable GPU and the uplink on the testbed is limited, we decided to equip the mobile robot with a mini-PC zbox en3070 on which the human detection algorithm runs. If an observation takes place inside or outside the safety zone defined around the deconstruction robot, the following event is logged, and an alert message is sent to the operator (see Figure 4.11). When the operator receives no warning, he/she starts or continues the motion of the deconstruction robot.

```
---
Receive Timestamp. 2024-11-12 17:03:56.226482
Adjusted Frame ID: 31142
---
[ 22.82 5.3498 -0.35627]
['http://econom.one/CampusWeekDemo#kukaKaliWS', '-11.62', '1.479', '0.', '3.101', '360', '4.094']
Human recognized outside safety zone
Speed: 0.4ms pre-process, 4.8ms inference, 0.6ms NMS per image at shape (1, 3, 2048, 2048)
---
```

Figure 4.11: Human detection event log

4.4 Living lab on the controlled deconstruction process

The developments of the robotic deconstruction process are performed on the Reference Construction Site- located in Aachen, Germany. The testbed enables the configuration of network technologies and the integration of hardware and software components within the context of real-world construction scenarios. The evaluation of challenges and developments can be conducted in consideration of the dynamic and harsh environment.

5 Discussion of results

The integration of the XR application into the planning phase of the deconstruction process has demonstrated potential in enhancing operational efficiency and safety on construction sites. By enabling the visualization of internal elements and facilitating access to critical information regarding building element connections from 3D models, this approach supports a more informed decision-making process for operators. The transition from BIM models to linked building data models marks an important step towards improving interoperability; however, it also highlights challenges associated with varying levels of modeling detail across different trades and companies. While .ifc was established as a common exchange format, discrepancies in practical application have underscored the need for standardization in modeling practices to ensure comprehensive data retrieval.

Furthermore, the deployment of the AR application has revealed limitations concerning the precision of end effector positioning. The necessity for accurate alignment when using magnetic grippers is apparent, especially when handling heavy steel beams. Inadequate positioning can lead to not only operational inefficiencies but also pose risks of damage to both robotic systems and structural components. Addressing these precision issues through enhanced control mechanisms will be essential for advancing automation capabilities within deconstruction processes.

The implementation of a safety assistant system represents another critical advancement in promoting worker safety during deconstruction activities. By defining a safety zone around the deconstruction robot and utilizing coordinate transformation techniques, we can effectively monitor personnel proximity to hazardous areas. This capability allows for real-time identification of individuals within or outside designated safety zones, thereby enhancing situational awareness among operators. Currently, observation logs serve as valuable tools for decision-making; however, future developments should focus on visualizing these logs to provide immediate feedback on necessary actions. Such enhancements would not only streamline operations but also foster a safer working environment by ensuring that operators are promptly alerted to any potential hazards.

In conclusion, while significant strides have been made in integrating advanced technologies such as XR applications and robotics into deconstruction processes, ongoing efforts are required to address challenges related to data standardization, precision control, and safety monitoring. Continued research and development in these areas will be crucial for realizing the full potential of automated solutions in construction environments.

6 Outlook for 2025

In the forthcoming months, the project will progress towards the advancement of the overall deconstruction process. This contains the full deployment of services with the 5G network on site (see chapter 6.1) as well as the integration of the end effector with the KUKA KMR Iontec to grip and lift the deconstructed steel element (see chapter 6.2). Moreover, the focus will be on the joint use case for energy awareness, with the specific objective of gaining insight into and optimizing energy consumption in (de-)construction processes. This will entail the incorporation of energy analytics tools that facilitate real-time monitoring and comprehensive assessment of energy consumption across the various stages of deconstruction.

6.1 Implementation of machine-to-machine communication via 5G

In this current setup of XR for machine control, the joint rotations are sent from the XR app to the controller on the KUKA KMR Iontec via MQTT, the controller then moves the arms to the desired position. The MQTT broker that are hosted on the KUKA KMR Iontec is to be migrated to the edge server for a centralized control via 5G. This is done so that the data and information flow are centralized, which all of the messages from different sources can be subscribed. The process is divided into two steps because the XR application could not provide a precise enough positioning for the end effector to grip the building element. Two cameras are to be mounted on the KUKA KMR Iontec, an RGB camera and an RGBD camera. The RGB camera is used for fine positioning of the end effector while the second RGBD camera is used for safety purposes such as obstacle detection and distance estimation. The data from the RGBD camera is streamed to an edge server for detection algorithm and the processed data is redirected to the tablet of the operator to provide a higher degree of remote supervision. Furthermore, several related ontologies are adapted and referenced to describe the entire process formally in linked data fashion. The adapted ontologies will link different sub-processes and play a crucial role in defining a shared vocabulary and structured relationships for data interoperability, clarity, and organization.

6.2 Implementation of gripping and lifting of deconstructed element

After a rough positioning of the end-effector through the developed XR app, the motion for fine positioning will be developed. For this purpose, the camera on the end effector will detect another marker on the steel beam, that of which is chosen to be deconstructed. The algorithm of the fine positioning runs by calculating the position of the marker relative to position of the end effector. When the ideal position is reached, a combination of motion of translations and rotations for gripping the component is initiated. Once the ideal position for gripping is done, a certain current is sent to the controller of the magnetic end effector to be activated.

Figure 6.1 Visualisation of path motions from different perspectives.

On-site workers then unfasten the screws on the gripped building element. When the unfastening is done, the operator controls the KUKA KMR Iontec via a similar process using the AR application to lift and move the unfastened building element. When the arm has moved the building element to the desired location, the arm releases the building element onto a pallet or trailer for transportation. Figure 6.1 and Figure 6.2 show the initial and ending phase of the lifting of the building element. The developments of the processes are to be carried out in the coming months on the Reference Construction Site.

Figure 6.2 Visualization of initial lifting process.

Figure 6.3 Visualization of end position of the lifting process.

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